

A NON LOCAL DAMAGE MODEL FOR ADHESIVE INTERFACES

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the work is to propose a constitutive model and a numerical scheme for the analysis of the debonding process of quasi-brittle adhesives subjected to a unilateral contact with friction condition. The debonding process is described by a non local damage model consisting in two damage variables, one associated with mode I and the other with mode II, opening modes. The incorporation of the two damage variables allows the consideration of mixed crack opening modes associated with complex loading conditions. Plane stress condition and small deformation process are assumed. The non local damage model is based on a gradient enhanced approach and is entirely formulated within a consistent extended thermodynamic theory leading to a system of coupled differential equations. In order to solve the set of coupled differential equations one proposes a semi-implicit scheme, with respect to the time domain, and applies the Galerkin finite element method in the discretization of the space domain, leading to the development of an interface finite element. The proposed model showed to be capable of reproducing experimental tests of the type DCB (double cantilever beam), related to mode I of crack opening, employed for adhesive characterization, using quasi-brittle and a Three-Point Bending crack propagation test.

1 INTRODUCTION

A considerable effort has been done in studying unilateral contact with friction problems, see [10-11, 9, 12]. Also, some relevant effort has been done in studying the analysis of the coupling of adhesion, friction and unilateral contact conditions, see [2-8,1,13-18,22]. However, not much effort has been deployed in the proposition of non local models using a gradient damage approach, see [19-21,23] with an application in the scope of the coupling of adhesion, friction and unilateral contact, see [19].

The objective of this work is to present a consistent non local theory, based on a gradient damage model, that considers the coupling effect of adhesion, friction and unilateral contact that takes place in a debonding process. Here, one makes use of the classical Coulomb Frictional Law for describing the sliding friction phenomena.

2 THEORETICAL DEVELOPMENT

The objective of this work is to propose a non local interface model for the analysis of the unilateral contact with adhesion and friction condition that may exist at the interface between an inclusion and the matrix in which it is embedded. The proposed model is able to account for crack opening modes I, II and mixed mode I and II, which occur once loss of adherence takes place. In order to do so, one introduces the damage variables $d_N(\vec{x},t)$ and $d_T(\vec{x},t)$ responsible for the description of crack opening modes I and II respectively.

2.1 Definition of the problem

Here, one is interested in the class of 2D problems depicted in (Fig. 1). The body occupies an open bounded subset $\Omega \subset R^2$ and has an interface Σ subjected to unilateral contact with friction and adhesion conditions.

Figure 1: Definition of the problem.

The introduction of the interface Σ enables one to define the upper and lower displacement fields denoted respectively by $\bar{u}^+(\bar{x}, t)$ and $\bar{u}^-(\bar{x}, t)$. The positive and negative sides introduce the jump of the displacement field, given by, $[[\bar{u}(\bar{x}, t)]] = \bar{u}^+(\bar{x}, t) - \bar{u}^-(\bar{x}, t)$. With the objective of incorporating a neighbourhood dependency in the debonding process, which minimizes mesh sensitivity, one makes use of a first gradient theory in $d_N(\bar{x}, t)$ and $d_T(\bar{x}, t)$.

The jump of the displacement $[[\bar{u}(\bar{x}, t)]]$, and the adhesive damages, $d_N(\bar{x}, t)$ and $d_T(\bar{x}, t)$, are subjected on Σ to:

$$d_N(\bar{x}, t) \in [0, 1], \quad d_T(\bar{x}, t) \in [0, 1] \quad \text{and} \quad [[\bar{u}(\bar{x}, t)]] \cdot \bar{n}(\bar{x}, t) \leq 0. \quad (1)$$

Notice that the physical admissible states of the body must be confined to the set K_Σ , where $K_\Sigma = \{([[\bar{u}]], d_N, d_T) \mid d_N \in [0, 1], d_T \in [0, 1] \text{ and } [[\bar{u}]] \cdot \bar{n} \leq 0, \text{ on } \Sigma\}$. Here, the state domain will be extended to non physical admissible states by letting the free energy become $+\infty$ at non physical admissible states.

2.2 Principle of virtual power

Before one states the principle of virtual power, the virtual power of the internal, external, and inertial forces are introduced and the vector space \mathbf{W} is defined. Here, $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}_o \times \mathbf{W}_{\Sigma N} \times \mathbf{W}_{\Sigma T}$ where $\mathbf{W}_o = \{\bar{v} \mid v_i \in H^1(\Omega), \bar{v} = \bar{0} \text{ on } \Gamma_u\}$, $\mathbf{W}_{\Sigma N} = \{\gamma_N \mid \gamma_N \in H^1(\Sigma)\}$ and $\mathbf{W}_{\Sigma T} = \{\gamma_T \mid \gamma_T \in H^1(\Sigma)\}$.

Now, for every part $\vartheta \subset \Omega$ and $(\bar{v}, \gamma_N, \gamma_T) \in \mathbf{W}$, one considers: The virtual power of the internal forces to be given by

$$\hat{P}_{(i)} = -\int_{\vartheta} \bar{\sigma} : D(\bar{v}) d\vartheta - \int_{\Sigma \cap \vartheta} \{\bar{Q}_\Sigma \cdot [[\bar{v}]] + Y_N \gamma_N + \bar{J}_N \cdot \nabla \gamma_N + Y_T \gamma_T + \bar{J}_T \cdot \nabla \gamma_T\} d\Gamma, \quad (2)$$

where $D(\bar{v})$ represents the symmetric part of the gradient of the displacement field \bar{v} , \bar{Q}_Σ the traction on the interface, (Y_N, \bar{J}_N) the dual pair associated with $(\gamma_N, \nabla \gamma_N)$ and (Y_T, \bar{J}_T) the dual pair associated with $(\gamma_T, \nabla \gamma_T)$; The virtual power of the external forces to be given by

$$\hat{P}_{(e)} = \int_{\vartheta} \bar{b} \cdot \bar{v} d\vartheta + \int_{\partial \vartheta} \bar{t} \cdot \bar{v} d\Gamma + \int_{\Sigma \cap \vartheta} A_N \gamma_N d\Gamma + \int_{\partial \Sigma \cap \vartheta} a_N \gamma_N ds + \int_{\Sigma \cap \vartheta} A_T \gamma_T d\Gamma + \int_{\partial \Sigma \cap \vartheta} a_T \gamma_T ds \quad (3)$$

and The virtual power of the inertial forces to be given by

$$\hat{P}_{(a)} = \int_{\vartheta} \bar{\rho} \ddot{\bar{u}} \cdot \bar{v} d\vartheta \quad (4)$$

in which one neglects the inertial forces related to the adhesive element.

The principle of virtual power is stated as:

$$\hat{P}_{(i)} + \hat{P}_{(e)} = \hat{P}_{(a)}, \quad \forall (\bar{v}, \gamma_N, \gamma_T) \in \mathbf{W}. \quad (5)$$

From eq. (5) one derives the following strong form of the coupled system of differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{div}(\sigma) + \bar{b} &= \rho \ddot{u} \quad \text{in } \Omega \\ \bar{Q}_\Sigma &= -\sigma \bar{n} \quad \text{at } \Sigma \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma \bar{n} = \bar{t} \quad \text{at } \partial\vartheta \cap \Gamma_i; \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -Y_N + \operatorname{div}(\bar{J}_N) + A_N &= 0 \quad \text{in } \Sigma \\ \bar{J}_N \cdot \bar{n} &= a_N \quad \text{at } \partial\Sigma \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} -Y_T + \operatorname{div}(\bar{J}_T) + A_T &= 0 \quad \text{in } \Sigma \\ \bar{J}_T \cdot \bar{n} &= a_T \quad \text{at } \partial\Sigma. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

2.3 Conservation of energy

In order to derive the local form of the conservation of energy equation, one introduces the total energy of the system, which can be decomposed as follows:

$$E(\vartheta) = \int_{\vartheta} \rho e \, d\vartheta + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\vartheta} \rho \ddot{u} \cdot \ddot{u} \, d\vartheta + \int_{\Sigma \cap \vartheta} E_\Sigma \, d\Gamma, \quad (9)$$

where e is the internal energy per unit mass and E_Σ is an internal energy per unit area defined on the adhesive surface. For isothermal processes with no heat source one derives the local equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho \dot{e} &= \sigma \cdot D(\ddot{u}) \quad \text{in } \Omega \\ \dot{E}_\Sigma &= \bar{Q}_\Sigma \cdot [[\dot{u}]] + Y_N \dot{d}_N + \bar{J}_N \cdot \nabla \dot{d}_N + Y_T \dot{d}_T + \bar{J}_T \cdot \nabla \dot{d}_T \quad \text{on } \Sigma. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

2.4 Second principle of thermodynamics

One considers the entropy of the system, for an arbitrary part $\vartheta \subset \Omega$, to be given as:

$$\eta(\vartheta) = \int_{\vartheta} \rho s \, d\vartheta + \int_{\Sigma \cap \vartheta} S_\Sigma \, d\Gamma, \quad (11)$$

where s is the entropy per unit mass and S_Σ the entropy per unit surface. As a result, one derives

$$\rho T \dot{s} \geq 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad \text{and} \quad T \dot{S}_\Sigma \geq 0 \quad \text{on } \Sigma. \quad (12)$$

2.5 Method of local state equations

Here, one assumes the existence, for each part $\vartheta \subset \Omega$, of the free energy potential, denoted by $\Lambda(\vartheta, \bar{u}, d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T)$ and decomposed, for convenience, as

$$\Lambda(\vartheta, \bar{u}, d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) = \Lambda_\vartheta(\vartheta, \varepsilon(\bar{u})) + \Lambda_\Sigma(\vartheta, [[\bar{u}]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T), \quad (13)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_\vartheta(\vartheta, \varepsilon(\bar{u})) &= \int_{\vartheta} \rho \psi(\varepsilon(\bar{u})) \, d\vartheta \quad \text{and} \\ \Lambda_\Sigma(\vartheta, [[\bar{u}]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) &= \int_{\Sigma \cap \vartheta} \Psi_\Sigma([[\bar{u}]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) \, d\Gamma. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The functions $\psi(\varepsilon(\bar{u}))$ and $\Psi_\Sigma([[\bar{u}]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T)$ represent respectively the free energy density per unit of mass and the interface density of the free energy potential. These densities are defined as

$$\psi = e - Ts \text{ and } \Psi_\Sigma = E_\Sigma - TS_\Sigma. \quad (15)$$

The potentials $\psi(\varepsilon(\bar{u}))$ and $\Psi_\Sigma([\bar{u}], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T)$ may be extended for processes where $([\bar{u}], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) \notin \mathbf{K}_\Sigma$ by defining, in this case, that

$$\Psi_\Sigma([\bar{u}], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) = +\infty. \quad (16)$$

The extended density of the free energy, $\Psi_\Sigma^*([\bar{u}], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T)$, may be written as

$$\Psi_\Sigma^*([\bar{u}], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) = \Psi_\Sigma([\bar{u}], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) + I_{\mathbf{K}_\Sigma}([\bar{u}], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) \quad (17)$$

in which

$$I_{\mathbf{K}_\Sigma}([\bar{u}], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } ([\bar{u}], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) \in \mathbf{K}_\Sigma \\ +\infty, & \text{if } ([\bar{u}], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) \notin \mathbf{K}_\Sigma \end{cases}. \quad (18)$$

By considering: $[\bar{u}]$, d_N , ∇d_N , d_T , and ∇d_T to be sufficiently regular with respect to the time parameter t , the process to be isothermal with no heat sources, and the above properties to hold, one derives the following material derivatives

$$\dot{\Lambda}_\vartheta(\vartheta, \varepsilon(\bar{u})) = \int_{\vartheta} \rho \frac{\partial \psi(\varepsilon(\bar{u}))}{\partial \varepsilon} \cdot \dot{\varepsilon}(\bar{u}) \, d\vartheta \quad (19)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\Lambda}_\Sigma(\vartheta, [\bar{u}], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) &= \int_{\Sigma \cap \vartheta} \left\{ \bar{Q}_\Sigma^r \cdot [\bar{u}] + Y_N^r \dot{d}_N \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \bar{J}_N^r \cdot \nabla \dot{d}_N + Y_T^r \dot{d}_T + \bar{J}_T^r \cdot \nabla \dot{d}_T \right\} d\Gamma \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where $(\bar{Q}_\Sigma^r, Y_N^r, \bar{J}_N^r, Y_T^r, \bar{J}_T^r) \in \partial \Psi_\Sigma^*([\bar{u}], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T)$.

Now, defining $Q_{\Sigma N}^r = \bar{Q}_\Sigma^r \cdot \bar{n}$, $Q_{\Sigma T}^r = \bar{Q}_\Sigma^r \cdot \bar{e}_t$, $[[u_N]] = [[\bar{u}]] \cdot \bar{n}$ and $[[u_T]] = [[\bar{u}]] \cdot \bar{e}_t$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\Lambda}_\Sigma(\vartheta, [[u_N]], [[u_T]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) &= \int_{\Sigma \cap \vartheta} \left\{ Q_{\Sigma N}^r [[\dot{u}_N]] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + Q_{\Sigma T}^r [[\dot{u}_T]] + Y_N^r \dot{d}_N + \bar{J}_N^r \cdot \nabla \dot{d}_N + Y_T^r \dot{d}_T + \bar{J}_T^r \cdot \nabla \dot{d}_T \right\} d\Gamma. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Moreover, from the Clausius-Duhem inequality one derives

$$\sigma = \rho \frac{\partial \psi(\varepsilon(\bar{u}))}{\partial \varepsilon} \quad (22)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (Q_{\Sigma N} - Q_{\Sigma N}^r) [[\dot{u}_N]] + (Q_{\Sigma T} - Q_{\Sigma T}^r) [[\dot{u}_T]] + (Y_N - Y_N^r) \dot{d}_N \\ + (\bar{J}_N - \bar{J}_N^r) \cdot \nabla \dot{d}_N + (Y_T - Y_T^r) \dot{d}_T + (\bar{J}_T - \bar{J}_T^r) \cdot \nabla \dot{d}_T \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Thus, defining $Q_{\Sigma N}^i = Q_{\Sigma N} - Q_{\Sigma N}^r$, $Q_{\Sigma T}^i = Q_{\Sigma T} - Q_{\Sigma T}^r$, $Y_N^i = Y_N - Y_N^r$, $\bar{J}_N^i = \bar{J}_N - \bar{J}_N^r$, $Y_T^i = Y_T - Y_T^r$ and $\bar{J}_T^i = \bar{J}_T - \bar{J}_T^r$ and considering the dissipation to be related only to the debonding process, described by \dot{d}_N and \dot{d}_T , and the frictional process, described by $[[\dot{u}_T]]$, one derives

$$Q_{\Sigma N}^i = 0, \quad \bar{J}_N^i = \bar{0} \text{ and } \bar{J}_T^i = \bar{0}, \quad (24)$$

which leads to the following dissipation associated with the debonding and friction process:

$$\Delta_{\Sigma} = Q_{\Sigma T}^i [[\dot{u}_T]] + Y_N^i \dot{d}_N + Y_T^i \dot{d}_T \geq 0 \text{ on } \Sigma. \quad (25)$$

A stronger and sufficient condition for satisfying the Clausius-Duhem inequality is to enforce

$$Q_{\Sigma T}^i [[\dot{u}_T]] \geq 0 \text{ on } \Sigma \quad \text{and} \quad Y_N^i \dot{d}_N + Y_T^i \dot{d}_T \geq 0 \text{ on } \Sigma. \quad (26)$$

Moreover, one assumes the free energy potentials $\rho\psi(\varepsilon(\bar{u}))$ and $\Psi_{\Sigma}^* ([[u_N]], [[u_T]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T)$ to be given, in a general 3D case, as:

$$\rho\psi(\varepsilon(\bar{u})) = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ 2\mu \operatorname{tr} [\varepsilon(\bar{u})^2] + \lambda (\operatorname{tr} [\varepsilon(\bar{u})])^2 \right\} \quad (27)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{\Sigma} ([[u_N]], [[u_T]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) &= \Psi_{\Sigma 1} ([[u_N]], d_N) + \Psi_{\Sigma 2} ([[u_T]], d_T) \\ &+ \Psi_{\Sigma 3} ([[u_N]], [[u_T]], d_N, d_T) + \Psi_{\Sigma 4} (d_N, \nabla d_N) + \Psi_{\Sigma 5} (d_T, \nabla d_T) + \Psi_{\Sigma 6} (d_N) + \Psi_{\Sigma 7} (d_T) \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{\Sigma 1} ([[u_N]], d_N) &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ (1-d_N)^2 k_N \right\} [[u_N]]^2 \\ \Psi_{\Sigma 2} ([[u_T]], d_T) &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ (1-d_T)^2 k_T \right\} [[u_T]]^2 \\ \Psi_{\Sigma 3} ([[u_N]], [[u_T]], d_N, d_T) &= \left\{ (1-d_N)(1-d_T) k_{NT} \right\} [[u_N]] [[u_T]] \\ \Psi_{\Sigma 4} (d_N, \nabla d_N) &= \frac{1}{2} k_N^b \|\nabla d_N\|^2 \\ \Psi_{\Sigma 5} (d_T, \nabla d_T) &= \frac{1}{2} k_T^b \|\nabla d_T\|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{\Sigma 6} (d_N) &= -(1-d_N) Y_N^o - Y_N^o \left\{ d_N - \int_0^{d_N} \left[\frac{\xi}{(1-\xi)^{a_N} + \epsilon_Y} + (1-b_N \xi)(1-c_N \xi) \right] d\xi \right\} \\ \Psi_{\Sigma 7} (d_T) &= -(1-d_T) Y_T^o - Y_T^o \left\{ d_T - \int_0^{d_T} \left[\frac{\xi}{(1-\xi)^{a_T} + \epsilon_Y} + (1-b_T \xi)(1-c_T \xi) \right] d\xi \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

2.6 Regularization of the Free Energy Potential

In order to circumvent the non differentiability of the Helmholtz free energy potential, $\Psi_{\Sigma}^* ([[u_N]], [[u_T]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T)$, so that general well known algorithms can be applied, one employs a regularization process. The regularized Helmholtz free energy potential, $\Psi_{\Sigma}^{\eta} ([[u_N]], [[u_T]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T)$, is such that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\eta \rightarrow 0} \Psi_{\Sigma}^{\eta} ([[u_N]], [[u_T]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) \\ = \Psi_{\Sigma}^* ([[u_N]], [[u_T]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T). \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Here, one uses the regularization given by

$$\Psi_{\Sigma}^{\eta} ([[u_N]], [[u_T]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) = \Psi_{\Sigma} ([[u_N]], [[u_T]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T) \quad (32)$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2\eta_n} \left(\langle [[u_N]] \rangle^+ \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2\eta_n} \left\{ \left(\langle d_N - 1 \rangle^+ \right)^2 + \left(\langle d_T - 1 \rangle^+ \right)^2 \right\} + \frac{1}{2\eta_n} \left\{ \left(\langle -d_N \rangle^+ \right)^2 + \left(\langle -d_T \rangle^+ \right)^2 \right\}.$$

2.7 Complementary Laws and Equations

The dissipations related to the friction and debonding processes are described by complementary equations. In the case of the frictional and debonding processes, one assumes the existence of a pseudo potential of dissipation, $\Phi_\Sigma([[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T; \circ)$, with $(\circ) \equiv ([[u_N]], [[u_T]], d_N, \nabla d_N, d_T, \nabla d_T)$, defined on $\vartheta \cap \Sigma$, and given by

$$\Phi_\Sigma([[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T; \circ) = \Phi_{\Sigma_1}([[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T; \circ) + \Phi_{\Sigma_2}([[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T; \circ) + \Phi_{\Sigma_3}([[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T; \circ) \quad (33)$$

where

$$\Phi_{\Sigma_1}([[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T; \circ) = \int_{\vartheta \cap \Sigma} \phi_{\Sigma_1}([[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T; \circ) d\Gamma \quad (34)$$

$$\Phi_{\Sigma_2}([[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T; \circ) = \int_{\vartheta \cap \Sigma} \phi_{\Sigma_2}([[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T; \circ) d\Gamma$$

and

$$\Phi_{\Sigma_3}([[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T; \circ) = \int_{\vartheta \cap \Sigma} \phi_{\Sigma_3}([[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T; \circ) d\Gamma$$

The density functions ϕ_{Σ_1} , ϕ_{Σ_2} and ϕ_{Σ_3} are convex relatively to the flux variables $[[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T$, positive and null at the origin with $\text{rel int}(dom\phi_{\Sigma_1} \cap dom\phi_{\Sigma_2} \cap dom\phi_{\Sigma_3}) \neq \emptyset$. One assumes the density of the pseudo potential ϕ_{Σ_1} and ϕ_{Σ_2} to be given by

$$\phi_{\Sigma_1}(\dot{d}_N; \circ) = \frac{1}{2} c_{\Sigma_N} (\dot{d}_N)^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \phi_{\Sigma_2}(\dot{d}_T; \circ) = \frac{1}{2} c_{\Sigma_T} (\dot{d}_T)^2 \quad (35)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_{\Sigma_1} = \left\{ \dot{d}_N \mid \dot{d}_N \geq 0 \text{ on } \vartheta \cap \Sigma \times (0, t_o) \right\}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{\Sigma_2} = \left\{ \dot{d}_T \mid \dot{d}_T \geq 0 \text{ on } \vartheta \cap \Sigma \times (0, t_o) \right\}$ are satisfied.

The restriction on \dot{d}_N and \dot{d}_T are imposed in order to account for an irreversible debonding process.

Thus, one defines the extended density of the pseudo potential $\phi_{\Sigma_1}^*$ and $\phi_{\Sigma_2}^*$ to be

$$\phi_{\Sigma_1}^*(\dot{d}_N; \circ) = \phi_{\Sigma_1}(\dot{d}_N; \circ) + I_{\mathbf{K}_{\Sigma_1}}(\dot{d}_N; \circ) \quad \text{and} \quad \phi_{\Sigma_2}^*(\dot{d}_T; \circ) = \phi_{\Sigma_2}(\dot{d}_T; \circ) + I_{\mathbf{K}_{\Sigma_2}}(\dot{d}_T; \circ) \quad (36)$$

respectively. Applying the normal dissipation criterion gives $Y_N^i \in \partial \phi_{\Sigma_1}^*(\dot{d}_N; \circ)$ and $Y_T^i \in \partial \phi_{\Sigma_2}^*(\dot{d}_T; \circ)$.

In order to describe the frictional process, one makes use of the classical Coulomb law of friction. In this case, the density of dissipation function ϕ_{Σ_3} is given by

$$\phi_{\Sigma_3}([[u_N]], [[u_T]], \dot{d}_N, \nabla \dot{d}_N, \dot{d}_T, \nabla \dot{d}_T; \circ) = \mu_\Sigma \left| Q_{\Sigma_N}^r([[u_N]], d_N, d_T) \right| \left| [[\dot{u}_T]] \right| \quad (37)$$

Hence, by applying the normal dissipation criterion, gives

$$Q_\Sigma^i \in \partial \phi_{\Sigma_3}([[u_T]]; [[u_N]], d_N, d_T). \quad (38)$$

2.7 Regularization of the frictional pseudo potential of dissipation

In order to circumvent the non differentiability of the frictional pseudo potential of dissipation $\Phi_{\Sigma_3}([[u_T]]; [[u_N]], d_N, d_T)$, associated with the Coulomb law, one employs a regularization process.

The regularized frictional pseudo potential of dissipation, $\Phi_{\Sigma_3}^\epsilon([[u_T]]; [[u_N]], d_N, d_T)$, is such that

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \Phi_{\Sigma_3}^\varepsilon ([[\dot{u}_T]]; [[u_N]], d_N, d_T) = \Phi_{\Sigma_3} ([[\dot{u}_T]]; [[u_N]], d_N, d_T) \quad (39)$$

and given by

$$\Phi_{\Sigma_3}^\varepsilon ([[\dot{u}_T]]; [[u_N]], d_N, d_T) = \int_{\partial \cap \Sigma} \phi_{\Sigma_3}^\varepsilon ([[\dot{u}_T]]; [[u_N]], d_N, d_T) d\Gamma \quad (40)$$

$$\phi_{\Sigma_3}^\varepsilon ([[\dot{u}_T]]; [[u_N]], d_N, d_T) = \mu_\Sigma \left| \mathcal{Q}_{\Sigma_N}^r ([[u_N]], d_N, d_T) \right| \phi_{\Sigma_3}^\varepsilon ([[\dot{u}_T]])$$

with

$$\phi_{\Sigma_3}^{\varepsilon_o}(x) = \begin{cases} \left(x - \frac{\varepsilon_o}{2}\right), & \text{if } x \geq \varepsilon_o \\ \frac{1}{2\varepsilon_o} x^2, & \text{if } |x| < \varepsilon_o \\ \left(-x - \frac{\varepsilon_o}{2}\right), & \text{if } x \leq -\varepsilon_o \end{cases} \quad (41)$$

for some $\varepsilon_o > 0$.

The pseudo potentials of dissipation $\Phi_{\Sigma_1}^*(\dot{d}_N; \circ)$ and $\Phi_{\Sigma_2}^*(\dot{d}_T; \circ)$ are also regularized and such that

$$\lim_{\eta \rightarrow 0} \Phi_{\Sigma_1}^\eta(\dot{d}_N; \circ) = \Phi_{\Sigma_1}^*(\dot{d}_N; \circ) \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{\eta \rightarrow 0} \Phi_{\Sigma_2}^\eta(\dot{d}_T; \circ) = \Phi_{\Sigma_2}^*(\dot{d}_T; \circ) \quad (42)$$

and given by

$$\Phi_{\Sigma_1}^*(\dot{d}_N; \circ) = \int_{\partial \cap \Sigma} \phi_{\Sigma_1}^\eta(\dot{d}_N; \circ) d\Gamma \quad \text{and} \quad \Phi_{\Sigma_2}^*(\dot{d}_T; \circ) = \int_{\partial \cap \Sigma} \phi_{\Sigma_2}^\eta(\dot{d}_T; \circ) d\Gamma \quad (43)$$

in which

$$\phi_{\Sigma_1}^\eta(\dot{d}_N; \circ) = \frac{1}{2} c_{\Sigma_N} (\dot{d}_N)^2 + \frac{1}{2\eta} \left(\langle -\dot{d}_N \rangle^+ \right)^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \phi_{\Sigma_2}^\eta(\dot{d}_T; \circ) = \frac{1}{2} c_{\Sigma_T} (\dot{d}_T)^2 + \frac{1}{2\eta} \left(\langle -\dot{d}_T \rangle^+ \right)^2. \quad (44)$$

2.8 Regularized interface constitutive relations

As a result of the regularization processes, one derives the following interface constitutive model:

$$\mathcal{Q}_{\Sigma_N}^r = \left\{ (1-d_N)^2 k_N \right\} [[u_N]] + \frac{1}{\eta_a} \langle [[u_N]] \rangle^+ + \left\{ (1-d_N)(1-d_T) k_{NT} \right\} [[u_T]] \quad (45)$$

$$\mathcal{Q}_{\Sigma_T}^r = + \left\{ (1-d_N)(1-d_T) k_{NT} \right\} [[u_N]] \left\{ (1-d_T)^2 k_T \right\} [[u_T]] \quad (46)$$

$$Y_N^r = -(1-d_N) k_N [[u_N]]^2 - (1-d_T) k_{NT} [[u_N]] [[u_T]] - \frac{1}{\eta_a} \langle -d_N \rangle^+ + \frac{1}{\eta_a} \langle d_N - 1 \rangle^+ \quad (47)$$

$$+ Y_N^o \left(\frac{d_N}{(1-d_N)^{a_N} + \varepsilon_Y} + (1-b_N d_N)(1-c_N d_N) \right)$$

$$Y_T^r = -(1-d_T) k_T [[u_T]]^2 - (1-d_N) k_{NT} [[u_N]] [[u_T]] - \frac{1}{\eta_a} \langle -d_T \rangle^+ + \frac{1}{\eta_a} \langle d_T - 1 \rangle^+ \quad (48)$$

$$+ Y_T^o \left(\frac{d_T}{(1-d_T)^{a_T} + \varepsilon_Y} + (1-b_T d_T)(1-c_T d_T) \right)$$

$$\vec{J}_N = k_N^b \nabla d_N \quad \text{and} \quad \vec{J}_T = k_T^b \nabla d_T \quad (49)$$

$$Q_{\Sigma}^i = \mu_{\Sigma} \left| Q_{\Sigma N}^r ([u_N]), d_N, d_T \right| \frac{d\phi_{\Sigma 3}^e(x)}{dx} \Big|_{x=[\dot{u}_T]} \quad (50)$$

$$Y_N^i = c_{\Sigma N} \dot{d}_N + \frac{1}{\eta} \langle -\dot{d}_N \rangle^+ \quad \text{and} \quad Y_T^i = c_{\Sigma T} \dot{d}_T + \frac{1}{\eta} \langle -\dot{d}_T \rangle^+ \quad (51)$$

2.9 Incremental weak formulation of the coupled mechanical damage problem

Here, the solution is considered known in the interval $[0, t_n]$ and the objective consists in the determination of the solution at t_{n+1} . Thus, by applying a semi-implicit algorithm where

$$\bar{u}_{n+1} = \bar{u}_n + \Delta \bar{u}_n, \quad d_{N_{n+1}} = d_{N_n} + \Delta d_{N_n} \quad \text{and} \quad d_{T_{n+1}} = d_{T_n} + \Delta d_{T_n} \quad (52)$$

one may derive the incremental weak formulation of the coupled mechanical damage problem, stated as: Given $(\bar{u}_n, d_{N_n}, d_{T_n})$, determine $(\bar{u}_{n+1}, d_{N_{n+1}}, d_{T_{n+1}}) \in \mathbf{K}$ so that

$$F_1(\bar{u}_{n+1}, d_{N_{n+1}}, d_{T_{n+1}}; \bar{w}) = \int_{\Omega} \sigma(\bar{u}_{n+1}) \cdot D(\bar{w}) \, d\Omega + \int_{\Sigma} Q_{\Sigma T}(\bar{u}_{n+1}, d_{N_{n+1}}, d_{T_{n+1}}) [[w_T]] \, d\Gamma \quad (53)$$

$$+ \int_{\Sigma} Q_{\Sigma N}(\bar{u}_{n+1}, d_{N_{n+1}}, d_{T_{n+1}}) [[w_N]] \, d\Gamma - \int_{\Gamma} \bar{t}_{n+1} \cdot \bar{w} \, d\Gamma - \int_{\Omega} \bar{b}_{n+1} \cdot \bar{w} \, d\Omega = 0, \quad \forall \bar{w} \in \mathbf{V}_u$$

$$F_2(\bar{u}_{n+1}, d_{N_{n+1}}, d_{T_{n+1}}; \gamma_N) = \int_{\Sigma} d_{N_{n+1}} \gamma_N \, d\Gamma + \frac{\Delta t k_N^b}{c_{\Sigma N}} \int_{\Sigma} \nabla d_{N_{n+1}} \cdot \nabla \gamma_N \, d\Gamma \quad (54)$$

$$- \frac{\Delta t}{c_{\Sigma N}} \int_{\Sigma} \langle -Y_N^r(\bar{u}_n, d_{N_n}, d_{T_n}) \rangle^+ \gamma_N \, d\Gamma - \int_{\Sigma} d_{N_n} \gamma_N \, d\Gamma = 0, \quad \forall \gamma_N \in \mathbf{V}_{\gamma_N}$$

and

$$F_3(\bar{u}_{n+1}, d_{N_{n+1}}, d_{T_{n+1}}; \gamma_T) = \int_{\Sigma} d_{T_{n+1}} \gamma_T \, d\Gamma + \frac{\Delta t k_T^b}{c_{\Sigma T}} \int_{\Sigma} \nabla d_{T_{n+1}} \cdot \nabla \gamma_T \, d\Gamma \quad (55)$$

$$- \frac{\Delta t}{c_{\Sigma T}} \int_{\Sigma} \langle -Y_T^r(\bar{u}_n, d_{N_n}, d_{T_n}) \rangle^+ \gamma_T \, d\Gamma - \int_{\Sigma} d_{T_n} \gamma_T \, d\Gamma = 0, \quad \forall \gamma_T \in \mathbf{V}_{\gamma_T}$$

3 SOLUTION CASES

The objective here is to investigate the adequacy of the proposed adhesive model and numerical scheme. In the following examples one used the parameters given in (Table 1).

η_u	[m/Pa]	10^{-13}	k_N^b	[Nm]	0.2
η_u	[m/Pa]	10^{-8}	k_T^b	[Nm]	0.2
μ_{Σ}		0.12			

Table 1: General parameters used in all the models

3.1 Double cantilever beam Problem DCB - case(1)

Here, one considers the DCB problem defined in [15] and depicted in (Fig. 2)

Figure 2: Description of the DCB problems.

In order to solve the problem a uniform mesh with 59 by 8 elements, representing 472 Quad9 elements, using 39 quadratic interface element applied at the middle of the mesh, whose domain is shown in (Fig. 1), is employed. The parameters of the model employed in problem cases (1) and (2) are given in (Table 2)

		Case (1)	Case(2)
L	[m]	0.1927	0.140
h	[m]	0.0127	0.0024
t_a	[m]	0.0002	0.0002
a_o	[m]	0.065	0.0055
adhesive		XN1244	Araldite

Table 2: Parameters used in DCB problem cases.

The result of the analysis is depicted in (Fig. 3) where the Young's modulus $E = 205GPa$ and the Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$.

Figure 3: Tip opening versus normal load.

The adhesive properties for problem case (1) in given in (Table 3). The same properties are used for both the normal and tangential parameters.

		Identification			Identification
$k_{N,T}$	[Pa / m]	2.5E8	$b_{N,T}$		-6.0
k_{NT}	[Pa / m]	2.5E7	$c_{N,T}$		-7.0
$a_{N,T}$		3.5	$Y_{N,T}^0$	[N / m]	1.0
$c_{\Sigma N, \Sigma T}$	[N sec / m]	1.0			

Table 3: Adhesive properties for problem case (1).

3.2 Double cantilever beam Problem DCB - case(2)

Here a uniform mesh of 4 by 140 element is used in which was employed 560 Quad9 elements and 85 interface elements. The result of the analysis is depicted in (Fig. 4). Here, also, the Young's modulus $E = 205GPa$ and the Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$. The DCB problem defined here is the one given in [15].

Figure 4: Tip opening versus normal load.

The adhesive properties employed in this case are given in (Table 4). Moreover, the same properties were used for both normal and tangential parameters.

		Identification		Identification	
$k_{N,T}$	[Pa / m]	$2.4E6$	$b_{N,T}$		-5.0
k_{NT}	[Pa / m]	$2.4E5$	$c_{N,T}$		-6.0
$a_{N,T}$		2.7	$Y_{N,T}^0$	[N / m]	0.8
$c_{\Sigma N, \Sigma T}$	[N sec / m]	1.0			

Table 4: Adhesive properties for problem case (2).

3.3 Three point bending test

In this case, one considers the Three point bending test problem given in [14] and described in (Fig. 5),

Figure 5: Description of the three point bending test.

where $L=2m$ and $h=2.0mm$. Here a mesh with 1600 Quad9 elements were used together with 20 interface elements. Here, the Young's modulus $E = 30GPa$ and the Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$. The

adhesive properties are given in (Table 5)

Identification			Identification		
$k_{N,T}$	[Pa / m]	8.7E8	$b_{N,T}$		-1.0
k_{NT}	[Pa / m]	8.7E7	$c_{N,T}$		-2.0
$a_{N,T}$		0.1	$Y_{N,T}^0$	[N / m]	0.5
$c_{\Sigma N, \Sigma T}$	[N sec / m]	0.4			

Table 5: Adhesive properties for the three point bending test

The result of the analysis is depicted in (Fig. 6)

Figure 6: Tip displacement versus normal load.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The proposed non local damage model for the analysis of the debonding process that can occur in the interface of composite materials showed to generate adequate fittings for the set of experimental data analyzed. The model incorporates the unilateral contact with friction condition that takes place once debonding takes place. The algorithm showed to be robust for the problem cases investigated. However, the model is a blunt type of model and can be improved by considering a better description of the singularities that occur after loss of adherence. This can be improved by using some XFEM approach, see [24]. Moreover, more research need to be done in order to consider viscous type of adhesive, with a ductile behaviour. Another point is the consideration of different debonding criterion that could be implemented in the differential equations related to the evolution of the damage variables.

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